

PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND HEALTHY LIFESTYLE OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article shows that the factors for maintaining the physical fitness of primary school students are based on a healthy lifestyle. Currently, the development of the psychophysiological well-being of primary school students through physical education is becoming relevant. The main role in the educational process is played by the formation of physical culture. In the process of training and education, the student, having mastered the methods and techniques of health care, must understand that this is vitally necessary. The relevance of physical education for primary school students is inextricably linked with the issues of preserving, strengthening and improving the health of the student. The development of students' physical culture is one of the processes in society that requires both complex and systematic work. The form of physical education activity is physical culture.*

Keywords: *comparative analysis, preschool education, concept, pedagogy, psychology, education.*

Recently, many studies and regulatory documents have shown that the basis for maintaining physical culture is a healthy lifestyle. Health problems are considered fundamental problems in scientific research. Physical culture is considered from an open informational and preventive problem to a sanitary and hygienic one, as socially and medically significant.

As for the concept of culture as a whole, culture is a concept that, together with the individual qualities of a person, includes national identity, traditions and all spiritual and material wealth [1]. Man is both a creator of culture and a consumer. Culture is a person's spiritual search, a creative experience. Culture is the renewal by man of social existence, everyday life and everyday life. Thus, culture is a product of human mental activity [2]. Culture is a feature of human labor, the changes that are introduced by human activity. Culture is the purpose and value of human existence. Culture is divided into material and spiritual. Part of the concept of culture is physical development and human health. Physical culture is the result of the formation of human physical nature. Physical education is the key to maintaining physical fitness.

Physical culture is the process of strengthening a person's physical strength, the physical development of his body through physical exercise. The main way to maintain physical culture is physical education. Physical education is a pedagogical system that is closely related to physical education lessons and sporting events. We can say that physical education ensures the qualitative development of the body. Physical culture is a type of culture that is created to improve a person's physical culture. Physical culture is closely related to strengthening, maintaining health, and creating a healthy lifestyle. This is a healing system aimed at physical development, strengthening the functioning of the body and hardening the body's organs.

Physical culture as a psychological and pedagogical component of a child's personality, concept of counting (O. S. Grebenyuk, A. V. Mudrik, M. I. Rozhkov); the main problem of

forming a child's social environment is the concept of counting (N. M. Talanchuk, V. P. Sozonov); theory of social support for children of primary school age (L. I. Aksenova, A. V. Mudrik, Kh. T. Sheryazdanova, Yu. N. Galaguzova, B. A. Raschetina, A. A. Tynyshbaeva); concept of readiness to work with children (Menlibekova G. Zh.) [3].

The works of T. I. Dyakonova, I. M. Mikhailitskaya, S. V. Yaoseva discuss in detail the issue of establishing relationships with students in the education system. Both parents and teachers have a great influence on a child's upbringing. Family members, parents, grandparents, brothers and sisters are all members of the same organization. Thus, a family is an environment in which a child, taking into account his personality and mental development, forms his surname as a worthy generation. Therefore, the family is of great importance in the formation of personality.

The purpose of physical education for primary school students: the formation of a healthy lifestyle, physical development and sanitary and hygienic skills.

Objectives of physical culture:

- maintaining and strengthening health;
- increasing the child's ability for physical labor;
- increasing responsibility for staying away from factors harmful to the child's health;
- formation of a critical attitude towards environmental conditions.

Necessary conditions for the formation of physical culture of primary school students:

- good knowledge of individual temperament, character traits, tastes and attitudes of students;

- determine the level of development in students of the qualities of interest, motivation, value judgments, etc.;

- gradually complicate the work of involving students in educational activities;

- change educational tactics if difficulties arise for students;

- more confidence in students' own activity and strengths;

- guide students to success, controlling the activity and independence of students.

Physical culture of a primary school student - includes all indicators in terms of the child's physical maturity. The development of physical culture is carried out by setting the following tasks: health, upbringing, education [6].

The goal of health improvement is to improve, strengthen the student's health, and enhance the formation of posture. The educational task is to develop physical and spiritual strength together, in harmony, to make efforts, to teach them to comply with hygiene requirements. The task of education is to teach the ability to apply a knowledge base aimed at developing certain motor skills and abilities in various life situations.

It is important to strictly follow the rules of physical education in class, as well as during walks. This is because cleanliness is the key to health everywhere. All students with good or poor performance in the class take an active part in the games. The purpose, content, means and elements of the game are determined in accordance with the age characteristics and abilities of the child, as well as the capabilities of physical strength [7].

The way to preserve physical culture is physical education, which differs from other types of physical education: firstly, the formation of skills and habits that are effective in the development of physical qualities; secondly, arming with knowledge that develops morpho functional qualities; thirdly, helping to improve labor performance.

Primary school students' bodies are growing rapidly, and their bodies are growing rapidly. The legs develop especially quickly. In elementary school, a student gains 2 kg per year. In elementary school, a student's bones begin to harden quickly. However, bone tissue still contains more organic matter and less mineral salts. Therefore, the pupil bone is flexible, chronic, and not yet fully hardened cartilaginous [6]. At the age of 7 years, the entire spine becomes clearly mature and defined. In girls aged 7-11 years, in boys aged 7-13 years, a cartilaginous layer remains between the epiphyses of the spine. The vertebrae become rigid at the age of 14-15 years.

Given these characteristics of students, it is necessary to give them a small amount of immobility exercises. For example, it is unacceptable to give exercises for jumping from great heights or jumping on a hard surface. They have weak spinal connections and muscles, and the cartilage between the vertebrae is thicker. To develop physical culture, it is necessary to intensify work on physical education. Most of the work done in physical education consists of physical exercises and sports games. Exercise is the basis of movement [5].

Physical activity of the body is the only way to improve the level of metabolic processes in the body and the condition of bones, muscles and the cardiovascular system. The need of a schoolchild's body for physical activity is different for everyone. Health is closely related to three aspects: physical, mental and social well-being. According to the definition of the World Health Organization, habitual movement is a type of movement aimed at satisfying natural human needs. Specially organized physical activity in elementary school includes types of physical exercise, diligent study, and walking. The body movements of elementary school students show normal development. At the same time, it increases the body's resistance to various diseases. The possibilities of body movement and bodily activity are interconnected.

The main means of physical culture are: physical exercises; games; tourism; gymnastics; sport; natural factors.

Physical exercises - improve the muscular system, blood circulation, respiratory function of the student. Physical education is a pedagogical system closely related to physical education. We can say that physical education ensures the qualitative development of the body. The game develops speed, endurance, and dexterity of the student. Tourism instills in students collectivism, hard work, tolerance and the ability to overcome difficulties. Gymnastics is divided into basic and hygienic, sports, acrobatic, artistic, industrial, and therapeutic. Sport is the main means of physical education, developing physical strength, will and health of students. Natural factors - sun, air, water, swimming, etc.

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